

ISic0584

Funerary inscription for Marcus Limbricius and his wife Helvia Arura

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tablet

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe

Autopsy

2019-07-11

Last Change

2019-07-15 - Jonathan Prag revised the file based on autopsy

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

First reported by Antonio Agustín in the church of S. Maria dei Palazzi ; lost by the time of Castelli, Principe di Torremuzza (later C18); rediscovered in 1987 in one of the adjoining buildings.

Coordinates

37.996456, 14.261844

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 20273

Physical Description

A thick tablet of compact white limestone. The lower left and lower right corners are lost, and the slab is cracked in half vertically down the middle. Left edge is finished smooth and straight; top edge is lightly cut back to the rear and rough; the right and lower edges preserve a carefully cut moulding, which strongly implies that the slab has been re-used from a previous base or other structure.

Dimensions

Height 37 cm

Width 51.8 cm

Depth 5.4 cm

Layout

Latin text preserved in full over four lines, vertically centred on the stone, with a vacat below. The first line is the largest, the third line smallest and most compressed.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are large and simply cut, without serifs. M has hastae of equal length, all off-vertical; S is shallow; R is closed with a long tail extending from the eye; B has small upper eye, closed; V is wide; F has shorter lower bar; E has equal short bars; C is not perfectly curved/circular, but rather shallow. Interpuncts throughout, formed of light vertical strokes.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 42-45 mm

Line 2: 38-42 mm

Line 3: 33-38 mm

Line 4: 36-40 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 17-20 mm

Interlineation line 2 to 3: 18-20 mm

Interlineation line 3 to 4: 14-17 mm

Text

1. M(arcus) · Limbricius · M(arci) · f(ilius) ·
2. Fal(erna tribu) · Rufus ·
3. v(ivens) · sibi · et · Helviae · Arurae
4. uxori · suae ·

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Marcus Limbricius Rufus, son of Marcus, of the Falerna tribe (set this up) while alive for himself and for his wife Helvia Arura.

Commentary

As a funerary inscription, this text must originally have stood with a tomb outside the city, before being transported at a later date to the church where it was first recorded in the sixteenth century in a manuscript of Atonio Agustín (Matritensis 5781 f.22 no.9, ap. Prestianni Giallombardo 1993a: Tav.1). The form of the letters suggests a text of the first century AD. Limbricius is probably of Campanian origin, and Puteoli specifically, as suggested by the other evidence for the family and tribe; Cicero attests to the interest of businessmen from Puteoli in Sicily (Verr. 2.5.154; see further Facella 2006: 210-211; the Falerna tribe is not otherwise attested in Sicily, see Prag 2010). The name Helvia is common, and Arura is one of a group of names linked to geographic origin and rural background.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491841

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